

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND
MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE
25 MARCH 2026, BRUSSELS

SETTING THE SCENE: THE ECOReFIBRE PROJECT

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What is the EcoReFibre Project?

- **Full name:** *Ecological Solutions for Recovery of Secondary Materials from Post-Consumer Fibreboards*
- **Funding:** Horizon 2020 (EU) under Grant Agreement n° 101057473; 12M €; 20 consortium partners
- **Duration:** May 2022 – October 2026

EcoReFibre – A collaborative project

- 10 industrial partners, 6 research institutes, 4 associations & consulting

EcoReFibre – Key Goal

Demonstrate viable recycling technologies to transform recovered waste wood into secondary raw materials for new wood-based products.

- Innovative sorting line
- Fibre extraction technologies
- **Position MDF as 100% recyclable**
- Support Green Deal & Circular Economy Act

Problem statement – Key drivers

- **Untapped potential of MDF waste** – Separation of fibreboard from recovered wood has not yet been possible on an industrial scale.
- **Existing routes** for post-consumer MDF – largely energy recovery – **are insufficient** to address the growing volume.
- **Reusing fibres** in high-quality materials **required new solutions** across disciplines + coordinated action by industry, science, and public actors.

Key barriers

- Regional disparities
- Fragmented and inconsistent collection systems
- Competition with energy recovery
- Physical and logistical constraints
- Economic viability

Material Flowchart

Waste fractions

Demonstration of processing technology

Secondary raw materials

Demonstration of final products

A, B, C, E, G : Demos at TRL 6/7
D, F: Demos at TRL 7

Work Package 1 – Waste provision

Waste fractions

Demonstration of processing technology

Secondary raw materials

Demonstration of final products

A, B, C, E, G : Demos at TRL 6/7
D, F: Demos at TRL 7

WP4: Sustainability, Health & Safety

Waste Fibreboard Availability

- Open-access model tool of historical and future waste fibreboard volumes (consumption and waste) in Europe by 2050
- Reliable prediction volumes for investors

Demo A – Smart sorting line

- Objective:

Separating fibreboard rich and solid wood fractions from wood waste (EWC 17 & 20)

Ensure purity >95%

- KPI: 500 kg/h **ACHIEVED**

Source: Dieffenbacher

Work Package 2 – Extraction of secondary materials

Demo B – Impact Reactor

Demo C – mTMP refiner

- Objective:

Extraction (dry/ wet) of fibres & fines from sorted fibreboard fractions and MDF processing residues

- KPI: 500 kg/h **ACHIEVED**

Source: Dieffenbacher

- Objective:

Thermo-mechanical processor - extracting fibres from sorted MDF and solid wood waste fractions

- KPI: 200 kg/day **ACHIEVED**

Source: IHD

Work Package 3 – Recycled fibres & fines into products

Demo D – Fines for particleboard surface layers

- Objective:
Incorporation of recycled fines into surface layers, to improve quality and reduce reliance on virgin materials
- KPI: Up to 20% recycled fibreboard fines in the surface layer **ACHIEVED**

Source: Sonae Arauco

Demo E1 – Construction block

- Objective:

Develop sustainable building blocks using 100% recycled MDF fines

- KPI: 600 units/day **ACHIEVED**

Source: Nibio

Demo E2 – Cyclic Thin Board (CTB)

- Objective:

Develop CTB using 100% recycled MDF fines.

- KPI: 300 m²/h **ACHIEVED**

Source: IHD

Demo F1 – HDF

- Objective and KPI:

Production trial of HDF with up to 25% recycled fibres **ACHIEVED**

Source: Homanit

Demo F2 – MDF

- Objective and KPI:

Production trial of MDF with up to 25% recycled fibres **IN PROGRESS**

Source: Sonae Arauco

Demo G1 – Rigid Insulation

- Objective and KPI:

ACHIEVED

Production trial with substitution level from 25% up to 100%

Source: Soprema

Demo G2 – Bulk insulation

- Objective and KPI:

ACHIEVED

Production trial with substitution level from 25% up to 100%

Source: Soprema

Demo G3 – Flexible insulation

- Objective and KPI:

ACHIEVED

Production trial with substitution level from 25% up to 100%

Source: Soprema

Lessons Learned

- **MDF is not only renewable – but now demonstrably recyclable :**

Industrial demo pilots show it is **technically** and **economically viable**, and **environmentally sound** to sort, defibrate, and recover high-quality fibres from post-consumer wood and fibreboard waste.

Demo results indicate that **products containing recycled fibres meet all standard performance requirements** for wood-based panels, **delivering quality without compromise.**

Thank you!

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